
Courtois NeuroMod

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Courtois NeuroMod team

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Note

The full dataset has not yet been officially released. This documentation describes the subset of data currently available.

The Courtois project on Neural Modelling (cneuromod) aims at training artificial neural networks using extensive experimental data on individual human brain activity and behaviour. Six subjects (three women, three men) were scanned weekly for five years (2018-23), with more sporadic scanning sessions still ongoing.

The cneuromod dataset currently features up to 200 hours of functional data per subject, including functional localizers (vision, language, memory, emotion), movies and video game play. So far functional neuroimaging data have been collected with functional magnetic resonance imaging and a variety of sensors (including electrodermal activity and oculometry). A smaller subset of data was collected with electroencephalography.

The cneuromod project is funded by a donation of the Courtois foundation. Courtois NeuroMod data are freely shared with the scientific community to advance research at the interface of neuroscience and artificial intelligence. Four subjects have shared their data without any restriction, while access to the full sample follows a registered access model.

An overview of the project is available on the cneuromod [website](#) and the technical documentation of the latest release is accessible [here](#).

DATASETS

1.1 BIDS

All functional and anatomical data have been formatted in [BIDS](#), for more information visit the [Brain Imaging Data Structure documentation site](#). Some of the files do not follow the main BIDS convention:

- Anatomical sequences with multiple contrasts are following [BEP001](#).
- Spinal cord imaging use Body Part tag proposed in [BEP025](#) (`bp-cspine`) to allow to distinguish them from brain anatomical images acquired with the same contrasts.

Note that BIDS session names have no meaning apart from being data acquired in the same session. The number of runs, the tasks and their order within each session will not match from one participant to another. Note that a few session indices are skipped if the whole session was discarded for various scanning issues.

1.2 Participants

Six healthy participants (aged 31 to 47 at the time of recruitment in 2018), 3 women (`sub-03`, `sub-04` and `sub-06`) and 3 men (`sub-01`, `sub-02` and `sub-05`) consented to participate in the Courtois Neuromod Project for at least 5 years. Three of the participants reported being native francophone speakers (`sub-01`, `sub-02` and `sub-04`), one as being a native anglophone (`sub-06`) and two as bilingual native speakers (`sub-03` and `sub-05`). All participants reported the right hand as being their dominant hand and reported being in good general health.

Exclusion criteria included visual or auditory impairments that would prevent participants from seeing and/or hearing stimuli in the scanner and major psychiatric or neurological problems. Standard exclusion criteria for MRI and MEG were also applied. Lastly, given that all stimuli and instructions are presented in English, all participants had to report having an advanced comprehension of the English language for inclusion.

1.3 anat

The anatomical dataset includes longitudinal anatomical images of the brain and upper spinal cord at an approximate rate of 4 sessions a year. The primary intended use of this dataset is to monitor the structural stability of the brain of participants for the duration of the study. Many quantitative measures of brain structure can also be derived and included in analyses, such as gray matter morphometry, tractography or measures of myelination. Cortical flat maps cut with `TkSurfer 6.0.0` are provided with the `freesurfer` derivatives for visualization.

The MRI sequences are described in more detailed in [Brain_anatomical_sequences](#) and [Spinal_cord_anatomical_sequences](#), including pdfs of the Siemens exam cards.

Brain T1w, T2w and DWI were copied from the HCP aging and development protocol for Prisma MRI scanner. Other sequences were selected and optimized by the Courtois NeuroMod team.

All images covering the face were anonymized by zeroing the data in the face, teeth and ears regions with a custom mask warped from the MNI space based on a linear registration of the T1w brain MRI series. This defacing script is available [here](#)

1.4 hcptrt

This `cneuromod` dataset is called HCP test-retest (`hcptrt`), because participants repeated 15 times the functional localizers developed by the Human Connectome Project, for a total of approximately 10 hours of functional data per subject. The protocol consisted of seven tasks, described below (text adapted from the [HCP protocol](#)). Before each task, participants were given detailed instructions and examples, as well as a practice run. A session was typically composed either of two repetitions of the HCP localizers, or one resting-state run and one HCP localizer. The e-prime scripts for preparation and presentation of the stimuli can be found in the [HCP database](#). Stimuli and e-prime scripts were provided by the Human Connectome Project, U-Minn Consortium (Principal Investigators: David Van Essen and Kamil Ugurbil; 1U54MH091657) funded by the 16 NIH Institutes and Centers that support the NIH Blueprint for Neuroscience Research, and by the McDonnell Center for Systems Neuroscience at Washington University. Note that in the `cneuromod` DataLad, functional runs are named `func_sub-<participant>_ses-<sess>_task-<task>_run-<run>`, where the `<participant>` tag includes `sub-01` to `sub-06`. For each functional run, a companion file `_events.tsv` contains the timing and type of events presented to the subject. Session tags `<sess>` are `001`, `002` etc, and the number and composition of sessions vary from subject to subject. The `<task>` tags are `restingstate`, `gambling`, `motor`, `social`, `wm`, `emotion`, `language` and `relational`, as described below. Tasks that were repeated twice have separate `<run>` tags (`01`, `02`).

Important

The duration of BOLD series are slightly varying across participants and repetitions. If consistent length is required by analysis, series can be trimmed at the end to match duration, task being aligned to the first TR.

1.4.1 Gambling

`gambling` duration: approximately 3 minutes. Participants were asked to guess whether a hidden number (represented by a “?” during 1500ms) was above or below 5 ([Delgado et al. 2000](#)). They indicated their choice using a button press, and were then shown the actual number. If they guessed correctly they were told they won money (+\$1.00, `win` trial), if they guessed incorrectly they were told they lost money (-\$0.50, `loss` trial), and if the number was exactly 5 they were told that they neither won or lost money (\$0, `neutral` trial). Note that no money was actually given to the participants and, as such, this task may not be an accurate reproduction of the HCP protocol. The conditions were presented in blocks of 8 trials of type `reward` (6 `win` trials pseudo randomly interleaved with either 1 `neutral` and 1 `loss` trial, 2 `neutral` trials, or 2 `loss` trials) or of type `punishment` (6 `loss` trials pseudo-randomly interleaved with either 1 `neutral` and 1 `win` trial, 2 `neutral` trials, or 2 `win` trials). There were four blocks per run (2 `reward` and 2 `punishment`), and two runs in total.

1.4.2 Motor

`motor` duration: approximately 3 minutes. This task was adapted from ([Buckner et al. 2011](#); [Yeo et al. 2011](#)). Participants were presented a visual cue, and were asked to either tap their left or right fingers (event types `left_hand` and `right_hand`, resp.), squeeze their left or right toes (event types `left_foot` and `right_foot`, resp.), or move their tongue to map motor area (event type `tongue`). Each movement lasted 12 seconds, and in total there were 13 blocks, with 2 of `tongue` movements, 4 of `hand` movements (2 `right_hand` and 2 `left_hand`), and 4 of `foot` movements (2 `right_foot` and 2 `left_foot`), and three 15 second fixation blocks where participants were instructed not to move anything. There were two runs in total, and 13 blocks per run.

1.4.3 Language processing

language duration: approximately 4 minutes. Participants were presented with two types of events. During story events, participants listened to an auditory story (5-9 sentences, about 20 seconds), followed by a two-alternative forced-choice question. During math events, they listened to a math problem (addition and subtraction only, varies in length), and were instructed to push a button to select the first or the second answer as being correct. The task was adaptive so that for every correct answer the level of difficulty increased. The math task was designed this way to maintain the same level of difficulty between participants. There were 2 runs, each with 4 story and 4 math blocks, interleaved.

1.4.4 Social cognition

social duration: approximately 3 minutes. Participants were presented with short video clips (20 seconds) of objects (squares, circles, triangles) that either interacted in some way (event type `mental`), or moved randomly on the screen (event type `random`) (Castelli et al. 2000; Wheatley et al. 2007). Following each clip, participants were asked to judge whether the objects had a “Mental interaction” (an interaction that appeared as if the shapes were taking into account each other’s feelings and thoughts), whether they were “Not Sure”, or if there was “No interaction”. Button presses were used to record their responses. In each of the two runs, participants viewed 5 `mental` videos and 5 `random` videos, and had 5 fixation blocks of 15 seconds each.

1.4.5 Relational processing

relational duration: approximately 3 minutes. Participants were shown 6 different shapes filled with 1 of 6 different textures (Smith et al. 2007). There were two conditions: relations processing (event type `relational`), and control matching condition (event type `control`). In the `relational` events, 2 pairs of objects were presented on the screen, with one pair at the top of the screen, and the other pair at the bottom. Participants were instructed to decide what dimension differed in the top pair (shape or texture), and then decide if the bottom pair differed, or not, on the same dimension (i.e. if the top pair differed in shape, did the bottom pair also differ in shape). Their answers were recorded by one of two button presses: “a” differ on same dimension; “b” don’t differ on same dimension. In the `control` events, participants were shown two objects at the top of the screen, and one object at the bottom of the screen, with a word in the middle of the screen (either “shape” or “texture”). They were told to decide whether the bottom object matched either of the top two objects on that dimension (i.e., if the word is “shape”, did the bottom object have the same shape as either of the top two objects). Participants responded “yes” or “no” using the button box. For the `relational` condition, the stimuli were presented for 3500 ms, with a 500 ms ITI, and there were four trials per block. In the `control` condition, stimuli were presented for 2800 ms, with a 400 ms ITI, and there were 5 trials per block. In total there were two runs, each with three `relational` blocks, three `control` blocks and three 16-second fixation blocks.

1.4.6 Emotion processing

emotion duration: approximately 2 minutes. Participants were shown triads of faces (event type `face`) or shapes (event type `shape`), and were asked to decide which of the shapes at the bottom of the screen matches the target face/shape at the top of the screen (adapted from Smith et al. 2007). Faces had either an angry or fearful expression. Faces, and shapes were presented in three blocks of 6 trials (3 `face` and 3 `shape`), with each trial lasting 2 seconds, followed by a 1 second inter-stimulus interval. Each block was preceded by a 3000 ms task cue (“shape” or “face”), so that each block was 21 seconds long, including the cue. In total there were two runs, three `face` blocks and three `shape` blocks, with 8 seconds of fixation at the end of each run.

1.4.7 Working memory

wm duration: approximately 5 minutes. There were two subtasks: a category specific representation, and a working memory task. Participants were presented with blocks of either places, tools, faces, and body parts. Within each run, all 4 types of stimuli were presented in block, with each block being labelled as a 2-back task (participants needed to indicate if they saw the same image two images back), or a version of a 0-back task (participants were shown a target at the start of the trial and they needed to indicate if the image that they were seeing matched the target). There were thus 8 different event types `<stim>_<back>`, where `<stim>` was one of `place`, `tools`, `face` or `body`, and `<back>` was one of `0back` or `2back`. Each image was presented for 2 seconds, followed by a 500 ms ITI. Stimuli were presented

for 2 seconds, followed by a 500 ms inter-task interval. Each of the 2 runs included 8 event types with 10 trials per type, as well as 4 fixations blocks (15 secs).

1.4.8 Resting state

restingstate duration: 15 minutes. In every other session, one resting-state fMRI run was acquired, giving 5 runs per participant. Participants were asked to have their eye open, be looking at fixation cross in the middle of the screen and be instructed to not fall asleep. A total of five resting-state fMRI runs were acquired per subject.

1.5 movie10

This dataset includes about 10 hours of functional data for all 6 participants. The python & psychopy scripts for preparation and presentation of the clips can be found in `src/tasks/video.py` of the following github [repository](#). Session tags `<sess>` were `001`, `002` etc, and the number and composition of sessions varied from subject to subject. The `<task>` tags used in DataLad corresponded to each movie (`bourne`, `wolf`, `life`, `figures`) and a numerical index of the segments shown as each movie was cut into roughly ten minutes segments presented in separate run. Exact cutting points were manually selected to not interrupt the narrative flow. Fade out to a black screen was added at the end of each clip, and with a few seconds overlap between the end of a clip and the beginning of the next clip. The movie segments can be found under `movie10/stimuli/<movie>/<movie>_seg<seg>.mkv`, and the functional runs are named `func_sub-<participant>_ses-<sess>_task-<movie><seg>`, where the `<participant>` tag ranges from `sub-01` to `sub-06`. A companion file `_events.tsv` contains the timing and type of conditions presented to the subject.

The participants watched the following movies ([cogatlas](#)):

- `<task>` name `bourne`: [The Bourne supremacy](#). Duration ~100 minutes.
- `<task>` name `wolf`: [The wolf of wall street](#). Duration ~170 minutes.
- `<task>` name `figures`: [Hidden figures](#). Duration ~120 minutes. This movie was presented twice, for a total duration of ~240 minutes.
- `<task>` name `life`: [Life Disc one of four: "Challenges of life, reptiles and amphibian mammals"](#). DVD set was narrated by David Attenborough. Duration, and lasted ~50 minutes. This movie was presented twice, for a total duration of ~100 minutes.

It should be noted that although three of the participants are not native anglophones, all participants watched the movies in English. The three native francophone participants are fluent in English and report regularly watching movies in English.

Important

The duration of BOLD series are slightly varying across participants and repetitions. If consistent length is required for analysis, series can be trimmed at the end to match duration, movie segments being aligned to the first TR.

Important

There are instances of re-scanned segments (due to scan QC fail), these re-scans will be in separate sessions. These should be handled or excluded in analysis requiring continuity of the presentation of the story.

1.6 Friends

This dataset contains functional data acquired while showing participants episodes of the Friends TV show in English. It includes seasons 1-6 for all subjects, except sub-04 who only completed seasons 1-4 (and a few segments of season 5). Each episode is cut in two ~12min segments (a/b) to allow more flexible scanning and give participants opportunities for breaks. There is a small overlap between the segments to allow participants to catch up with the storyline. The task BIDS entity identifies the season, episode and segments (a/b) as such `task-s<season>e<episode>[ab]`.

Important

A mistake happened when the pilot episode (s01e01) was accidentally skipped at the beginning of the first season. It was shown to participants after they had watched episodes s01e02 to s01e06, causing a slight disruption in the storyline. In the latest release, files have been renamed to match the episodes' intended order (rather than the order in which they were administered) and to be consistent with external data such as annotation corpora.

1.7 harrypotter

This dataset contains a single session per participant (N=5; sub-01, sub-02, sub-03, sub-05 and sub-06) when they read chapter 9 from Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone. The text was presented word by word, at a 2Hz pace (each word presented for .5s). This chapter was split over 7 runs of approximate equal length. The stimuli used in this dataset are taken from the experiment reported by [Wehbe et al. \(2014\)](#) for which a separate fMRI dataset (N=9) has been collected and shared.

1.8 gamepad

This dataset was acquired as a validation study of the CNeuroMod videogame controller. The CNeuroMod videogame controller is an open source, custom-built, fiber-optic, MRI compatible video game controller, designed by our team engineer, Mr. André Cyr, and described in [Harel et al. \(2023\)](#). For a detailed description of the controller, including building instructions visit this [site](#). The gamepad dataset contains both fMRI and behavioural data acquired on 4 participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03 and sub-06) during a simple cued-response task in which the participants were instructed to press the various controller buttons for short and long durations (5 blocs of 10 trials per condition).

For each subject we acquired 8 sessions, of two runs each. Four of the sessions were acquired in the MRI scanner using our typical setup (i.e 64-channel head coil) along with the MRI-compatible videogame controller, during which we acquired BOLD recordings. The four remaining sessions were acquired in our MRI simulator, with a mock 64-channel head coil, and using a [commercially available SNES-like controller](#). The latter served as a reference for our validation study. Mock and MRI sessions were alternated, and the starting order (mock or MRI first) was counterbalanced across subjects. For the MRI sessions, the behavioural data can be found in the `*_events.tsv` files stored in the `func` folder. For the mock sessions, behavioural data can be found in the `beh` folder.

1.9 shinobi_training

This is a pure behavioral dataset collected while participants trained at home on the videogame Shinobi III The Return of the Ninja Master, for N=4 participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-04 and sub-06). A subset of 3 levels of the game was selected for their similarity in terms of core gameplay although some mechanics were specific to each level. These levels were the same than those used in the `shinobi` dataset.

The participants were first introduced to the game by playing the Level-1 at least once. This level introduces the basic game mechanics (moving from left to right, avoid or kill enemies) at an abordable difficulty level for most players. Then, the participants were able to freely choose the level on which they played as well as the training sessions frequency. No training regimen was imposed to the participants making that dataset highly heterogeneous. The dataset consists of sessions of gameplay as collections of `.bk2` files recorded by the `gym-retro` API.

This dataset can be used to analyze learning or individual game-play styles, and can be investigated in conjunction with the fMRI dataset.

1.10 shinobi

This dataset contains about 10h of gameplay on the videogame Shinobi III The Return of the Ninja Master, for N=4 participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-04 and sub-06). Participants used the CNeuroMod videogame controller described in Harel et al. (2023). In each run, participants played 3 levels in cycles and always in the same order. These levels were selected in the game to have fairly homogeneous core game mechanics (see the [Sega documentation](#) for more details on game structure):

- Level-1 corresponded to round 1 of the original game, “Zeed’s Resurrection”. It included one mini-boss and one boss fight.
- Level-4 corresponded to the beginning of round 4 of the original game, “Destruction”. It included no mini-boss or boss fight.
- Level-5 corresponded to the beginning of round 5 of the original game, “Electric demon”. It included one mini-boss fight and no boss fight.

Participants moved to the next level if they successfully completed a level, or lost three lives. A new level was then initiated unless 10 minutes had elapsed from the start of the run, at which point the run ended. The duration of each run is thus variable to a degree, with a minimum of ten minutes. Due to the fixed order in the cycle, Level-1 was repeated more often than Level-4 and Level-5.

In this dataset and the related documentation, we use the term `run` to designate a single functional sequence acquisition (per the usual in neuroimaging). The term `repetition` is used to designate the play of a single level (from start to either completion or the loss of three lives). As such, each run contains around 3 to 5 repetitions.

For each functional run, a companion file `_events.tsv` contains the timing and duration of each repetition played, as well as a `_annotated_events.tsv` file that additionally contains richer annotations, including button presses, handcrafted annotations (Kills, Health losses), and frame-wise RAM values. Additional documentation on the available annotations can be [found here](#).

The companion `.bk2` files can be found in the `<participant>/<sess>/gamelogs` folder.

📌 Important

Due to a programming error a certain number of game recording files were lost during acquisition, these repetitions are still listed in the events file but their `stim_file` field is left blank. Choice is left to the user whether to exclude the corresponding fMRI volumes or not for their analysis.

1.11 mario

The mario dataset explores behavioural and brain correlates of videogame play and includes five participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03, sub-05 and sub-06; two females, three males) who played Super Mario Bros (SMB; Nintendo, 1985) inside an MRI scanner. The dataset comprises ~15h of fMRI data per subject. Among the participants, sub-01 had prior experience with SMB, and two participants (sub-01 and sub-02) reported regular videogame play. One participant (sub-06) reported no videogame experience, except another retro platformer called Shinobi III: Return of the Ninja Master (RotNM; Sega, 1993) she practiced for 10+hours as part of a prior CNeuroMod experiment (shinobi dataset).

To play the game, participants used the CNeuroMod videogame controller described in Harel et al. (2023). The game software was run on a console emulator using OpenAI’s gym-retro library (Nichol et al., 2018), a Python-based platform supporting emulators for over 10 retro consoles and thousands of games. Built on gym (Brockman et al., 2016), a library designed for reinforcement learning, gym-retro integrates console emulators via the Libretro API (Libretro, n.d.). In

this experiment, SMB was played and recorded at a 60Hz framerate. Because the game is fully deterministic, only player inputs (button presses) were recorded, enabling the reconstruction of exact replays of gameplay sequences.

SMB is a commercial platform side scroller game released in 1985 by the company Nintendo. The aim of the game is to go right and reach the end of each level, while avoiding a variety of obstacles and enemies. The platformers genre was selected by the CNeuroMod team because gym-retro was developed for a major reinforcement competition centered on this genre (OpenAI, 2018). This game was further selected for its compatibility with gym-retro and its commercial success, ensuring engaging gameplay but also extensive prior literature investigating the design of the game (Dahlskog & Togelius, 2012; Thompson, 2023). As in other platformers, players navigate a linear two-dimensional environment filled with enemies and obstacles to reach a destination. The player may collect some power ups which change the form and behaviour of the character in the game. For this study, 22 levels were selected for their gameplay similarity. Specifically, all original levels of SMB were used with the exception of the water and boss levels, which feature very different game mechanics than the other. Each attempt at completing a level began with no power up and three lives and is called a “repetition”. The attempt was completed if the player reached the end of the level or lost all three lives trying. When players died, they resumed their attempt from the start of the level, or from a dedicated spawn point only featured in some levels and selected by the original game designers. The participants first repeated each level until they could succeed at least once, with all the levels presented in order (Discovery phase). Then, they played randomly selected levels for the remaining sessions.

To facilitate the analysis of this dataset, two companion repositories are made availables :

- `mario.replays` : This codebase can be used to generate replays from the behavioral files of the mario dataset. For each repetition, it will create files containing metadata (.json), video (.gif, .mp4 or .webp) and memory or game variables dumps (.npz)
- `mario.scenes` : This codebase splits the 22 SMB levels used for this dataset into 313 smaller “scenes” (approx. 15 per level), which can be seen as atomic units of gameplay. These scenes are annotated with 23 elementary design patterns suggested by Dahlskog & Togelius, 2012, and complemented with 6 additional patterns (beginning, ending, bonus zone, waterworld, moving platform, and checkpoint) that provide additional context. The code in the repository can perform analysis on the scenes annotations, as well as generate clips from the behavioral data of the mario dataset. For each attempt at completing a scene, the code will create files containing metadata (.json), video (.gif, .mp4 or .webp) and memory or game variables dumps (.npz).

Sub-ject	Repe-titions (Discov-ery)	Repe-titions (Prac-tice)	Du-ration (Discov-ery)	Du-ration (Prac-tice)	Success rate (Dis-covery)	Success rate (Prac-tice)	Repe-titions (Total)	Suc-cess rate (Total)	Dura-tion (To-tal)
01	230	567	03:54:27	09:47:11	0.578261	0.781305	797	0.72271	13:41:38
02	227	487	04:57:35	12:30:24	0.400881	0.671458	714	0.585434	17:27:59
03	176	451	04:49:38	11:57:19	0.431818	0.698448	627	0.623604	16:46:57
05	177	457	05:30:04	12:27:44	0.367232	0.582057	634	0.522082	17:57:48
06	134	468	04:25:41	13:37:40	0.626866	0.856838	602	0.805648	18:03:22
To-tal	944	2430	23:37:27	60:20:19	0.481011	0.718021	3374	0.651896	83:57:47

1.12 Hearing safety protocol

This dataset contains behavioral and physiological data acquired through a variety of clinical audiology tests (see the [CNeuroMod docs](#) and [Fortier et al. \(2023\)](#) for details on the dataset’s context and acquisition). Participants underwent multiple test sessions (minimum = 4, maximum = 18, mean = 12, SD = 4.858) composed of different combinations of tests (experimental-condition dependant).

For each of the participants, a `_sessions.tsv` file lists the available test data for each of the sessions.

1.13 things

N=4 participants completed between 33 (sub-06) and 36 (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03) fMRI sessions of a continuous recognition task with images from the [THINGS dataset](#). The first session included 3 runs, and all subsequent sessions included 6 runs. Each 4.7 minutes run included 60 trials. For each trial, an image was shown in the center of the screen for 2.98s, followed by a 1.49s ISI. Subjects maintained fixation on a black fixation marker overlaid onto the image center and visible at all times throughout a run. Images were sampled from 720 THINGS categories. sub-01, sub-02, sub-03 were shown 6 images per category (4320 unique stimuli), and sub-06 was shown 5 images for 480 categories and 6 images for the remaining 240 (3840 unique stimuli).

Each image was shown three times throughout the duration of the experiment (it was repeated once within and once across weekly sessions). For each trial, participants reported whether the image was shown for the first time (“unseen”) or whether it had been shown previously (“seen”), either during the current or a previous session or both. Participants also reported whether or not they felt confident in their answer. Responses (seen/unseen \times sure/unsure) were made with the right thumb by pressing one of four buttons (top, bottom, left, right) on a video game controller designed by the team and described in [Harel et al. \(2022\)](#). No feedback on memory performance was given to participants throughout the entire duration of the experiment.

For each functional run, a companion file `_events.tsv` contains the timing and duration of each trial, the identity of the image shown, the condition (seen/unseen), whether the image was repeated between and/or within session, the subject’s response and whether it was correct, the delay and number of trials since the last presentation (for repeating items), and metrics of fixation compliance derived from eye-tracking data. Available trial annotations are described [here](#)

Important

A few sessions were accidentally administered out of the planned order, introducing atypical patterns of repetition for images shown during/after those sessions. Users may want to exclude these sessions from analyses that depend on repetition patterns or memory performance. These include `ses-024`, `ses-025` and `ses-026` for sub-03, and `ses-019` to `ses-026` (inclusively) for sub-06. fMRI data from run 6 of sub-06’s `ses-008` are excluded from the dataset due to mistakenly positioned MRI field-of-view.

1.14 retinotopy

Three participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03, sub-05) completed multiple sessions (6 for sub-01, sub-02 and sub-05, 5 for sub-03) of a retinotopy task adapted from [Kay et al. \(2013\)](#) and implemented in PsychoPy. This task was designed to derive population receptive field (pFR) properties at the voxel level and to delineate ROIs from the early visual cortex.

Each session included three 5-minutes functional runs, each of which used a different aperture shape : `ring`, `bar` or `wedge`. A run included eight cycles during which an aperture moved slowly across the stimulated visual field to reveal a portion of visual pattern designed to drive both low-level and high-level visual areas. Patterns were drawn randomly at a rate of 15 fps from the [Human Connectome Project retinotopy stimuli](#) (downloaded [here](#)).

The stimulated visual field was a circular area with a diameter corresponding to 10 degrees of visual angle. `ring` runs featured a thick circle aperture that expanded from and contracted toward the screen center. `wedge` runs featured a wedge aperture rotating clockwise and counter-clockwise. `bar` runs featured a wide bar aperture sweeping across the screen in 8 different directions. Participants fixated their gaze on a central dot and pressed a button with the right thumb on a custom mri-compatible video game controller ([Harel et al. \(2022\)](#)) whenever the dot changed color (alternating between blue and orange).

1.15 floc

Four participants (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03, sub-05) completed six sessions of a functional localizer task designed to identify brain regions responding preferentially to specific stimulus categories. The task was based on a [Psychopy implementation of the Stanford VPN lab's fLoc task](#) using stimuli from the fLoc functional localizer package (downloaded [here](#)).

Each session included two functional runs of 3.85 minutes with randomly ordered ~6s blocks of rapidly presented images from one of five categories : faces, places, bodies, objects and characters. Each block included 12 trials for which an image from the block's category was displayed centrally for 0.4s, followed by a 0.095-0.1s ISI. Subjects were instructed to fixate on a red dot in the middle of the screen and to press a button with the right thumb on a custom mri-compatible video game controller ([Harel et al. \(2022\)](#)) whenever the same image appeared twice in a row (the "one-back" task variation). Blocks of baseline condition during which the red fixation dot appeared on a grey background for 5.96s were also intermixed in the block sequence. Each run included 6 blocks from each of the five categories and 6 blocks of baseline. For each session, the first run included images from the house (places), body (body parts), word (characters), adult (faces) and car (objects) fLoc package sub-categories. The second run included images from the corridor (places), limb (body parts), word (characters), adult (faces) and instrument (objects) sub-categories.

ACCESS TO DATA

2.1 Partial fully unrestricted data access

Four CNeuroMod subjects (sub-01, sub-02, sub-03 and sub-05) have chosen to openly share their data via the Canadian Open Neuroscience Platform (CONP). These data are distributed under a liberal Creative Commons data license, in particular authorizing re-sharing of derivatives. Note that you can use the instructions in this guide directly - the command will retrieve all the CONP data and simply raise warnings about the other subjects, which require an access key to download (see next Section for full access).

2.2 Complete CNeuroMod databank via Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)

To access all the data available in the CNeuroMod databank (i.e all 6 subjects) researchers are required to complete a form with a brief description of planned analyses, and complete an inter-institutional data transfer agreement. Links to relevant forms can be found on the [access request page](#). The data transfer agreement must be signed by the researcher responsible for the project as well as a representative of the main academic institution where the research team is affiliated. The application will be evaluated by a data access committee and, if approved, a transfer key will be shared with the research team in order to transfer the data (see *Downloading the dataset* section below).

2.3 Ethics

The Courtois NeuroMod project has been approved by the institutional research ethics board of the [CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'île-de-Montréal](#). The CIUSSS is a large governmental health organization, and the core NeuroMod team is based at the Research Centre of the Montreal Geriatric Institute (CRIUGM), which is a part of the CIUSSS, and affiliated with the [University of Montreal](#). The consent forms signed by participants and the project description are available below. The formal authorization lettre from the ethics committee is available upon request. The project was most recently renewed by the [Comité d'éthique de la recherche — Vieillesse et neuroimagerie \(CER-VN\)](#) on October 21st, 2022 under the project number CER VN 18-19-22, and title “Extensive characterization of human brain activity under naturalistic stimulations for developing individual artificial neuronal models.”

- [courtois_neuromod_project_description.pdf](#): scientific overview of the Courtois NeuroMod project (in English).
- [consent_form_english.pdf](#): the informed consent form signed by participants (English version).
- [consent_form_french.pdf](#): the informed consent form signed by participants (French version).

2.4 Downloading the dataset

All data are made available as a [DataLad collection](#) on github in public repositories. [DataLad](#) is a tool for versioning a large data structure in a git repository. The dataset can be explored without downloading the data, and it is easy to only download the subset of the data you need for your project. See the [DataLad handbook](#) for further information.

We recommend creating an SSH key (if not already present) on the machine on which the dataset will be installed and adding it to github. See the official [github instructions](#) on how to create and add a key to your account.

To obtain the data, you need to install a recent version of the [DataLad software](#), available for Linux, OSX and Windows. Note that you need to have valid login credentials to access the NeuroMod git as well as the NeuroMod [Amazon S3](#) fileservers. Once you have obtained these credentials, you can proceed as follows in a terminal:

```
# Install recursively the dataset and subdataset of the current project.
# If using ssh git clone as follow, you can set your public SSH key in the present git,
↳to ease future updates.
datalad install -r git@github.com:courtois-neuromod/cneuromod.git
# If errors show up relative to .heudiconv subdataset/submodule, this is OK, they are
↳not published (will be cleaned up in the future).
cd cneuromod
```

2.4.1 Versioning

By default, this will install the latest stable release of the dataset, which is the recommended version to get for a new analysis. If you are need to work on a specific version (for instance to reproduce a result), you can change to the appropriate tag with.

```
git checkout 2020
```

We now set as environment variable the credentials to the file server. The s3 access_key and secret_key will be provided by the data manager after being granted access to cneuromod by the user access committee.

```
# This needs to be set in your `bash` everytime you want to download data.
export AWS_ACCESS_KEY_ID=<s3_access_key> AWS_SECRET_ACCESS_KEY=<s3_secret_key>
```

2.4.2 Preprocessed data

For analysis of fMRI data, it is preferable to directly get the preprocessed data (smriprep and fmriprep for now).

```
datalad install git@github.com:courtois-neuromod/cneuromod.processed.git
cd cneuromod.processed
```

You can install the sub-datasets you are interested in (instead of installing all of them) using for instance:

```
datalad get -n smriprep fmriprep/movie10
```

and then get only the files you need (for instance MNI space output):

```
datalad get smriprep/sub-*/anat/*space-MNI152Nlin2009cAsym_* # get all anatomical output,
↳in MNI space
datalad get fmriprep/movie10/sub-*/ses-*/func/*space-MNI152Nlin2009cAsym_* # get all,
↳functional output in MNI space
```

You can add the flag `-J n` to download files in parallel with `n` being the number of threads to use.

The source data used for preprocessing (including raw data) are referenced as sources in the preprocessed dataset following *Yoda*, so as to track provenance. You can also track the version of the cneuromod dataset you are using by installing it in a datalad dataset created for your project.

2.4.3 Stimuli and event files

You will likely need the events files and stimuli for your analysis which can be obtained from the sourcedata reference sub-datasets, for example:

```
datalad get -r fmrip/prepare/movie10/sourcedata/movie10/stimuli fmrip/prepare/movie10/sourcedata/  
↳movie10/*_events.tsv
```

or to get subject specific event files for tasks collecting behavioral responses:

```
datalad get -r fmrip/prepare/hcp/prepare/sourcedata/hcp/prepare/sub-*/ses-*/func/*_events.tsv
```

2.5 Updates

The dataset will be updated with new releases so you might want to get these changes (unless you are currently running analyses, or trying to reproduce results). The main branches of all datasets will always track the latest stable release.

```
# update the dataset recursively  
datalad update -r --merge --reobtain-data
```

Once your local dataset clone is updated, you might need to pull new data, as some files could have been added or modified. The `--reobtain-data` flag should automatically pull files that you had already downloaded in case these were modified.

3.1 Image acquisition

3.1.1 Scanner

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) for the Courtois neuromod project is being acquired at the functional neuroimaging unit (UNF), located at the “Centre de Recherche de l’Institut Universitaire de Gériatrie de Montréal” (CRIUGM) and affiliated with University of Montreal as well as the CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l’île-de-Montréal. The scanner is a Siemens Prisma Fit, equipped with a 2-channel transmit body coil and a 64-channel receive head/neck coil. Most imaging in the Courtois Neuromod project are composed solely of functional MRI runs. Periodically, an entire session is dedicated to anatomical scans.

3.1.2 Personalized head cases

In order to minimize movement, each participant wears a custom-designed, personalized headcase during scanning, built by Caseforge. The headcases are milled based on a head scan of each participant generated using a handheld 3D scanner, and the shape of the MRI coil. Caseforge mills the personalized headcases in polystyrene foam blocks.

3.1.3 Hearing protection

In order to provide an additional level of hearing protection against repeated exposure to the noise of the MR scanner, as well as optimize the quality of the auditory stimuli, we implemented two custom hearing protection set-ups for CNeuro-mod participants. The initial custom set-up was composed of the S15 MRI-compatible earphone system (Sensimetric), standard-sized disposable Comply canal tips (Hearing Components, Inc.; advertised Noise Reduction Rating: 29 dB), and modified commercial earmuffs (Stanley Black & Decker Inc; unmodified advertised Noise Reduction Rating: 27 dB). The commercial earmuffs were modified to render them thinner by cutting the inner section of the earmuff (i.e. leaving the external cup intact) and re-attaching the foam ring (i.e. foam that seals around the ear) to the modified earmuff. This modification was necessary to enable the earmuffs to fit inside the head coil (i.e. Siemen’s 64-channel), along with CaseForge headcases and the participants’ heads. This version of the custom hearing protection was eventually abandoned due to pressure points it caused on some participants’ jaws, particularly individuals with larger heads, and when worn for extended periods of time (i.e. 1h+).

This initial hearing protection set-up was used by participants for the following datasets:(hcptrt),(movie10), (friends) seasons 1-4, and (shinobi).

The second, and current, custom hearing protection set-up is again composed of the S15 MRI-compatible earphone system (Sensimetries Corporation), “custom” disposable Comply canal tips (Hearing Components, Inc., advertised Noise Reduction Rating: 29 dB), and headphone replacement memory foam rings (Brainwavz Audio). Additionally, each subject selected their “custom” Comply canal tip from one of two types of styles (original and short), each with three sizes (slim, standard, large), based on their ideal comfort level (i.e. fit based on their ear canal shape) and relative sense of optimal sound protection.

The second version of the custom hearing protection set-up, which is still currently in use, was used by participants for the (friends) seasons 5-6 datasets.

3.2 Sequences

3.2.1 Functional sequences

The parameters of the functional MRI sequence relevant for data analysis can be found in the NeuroMod DataLad. The functional acquisition parameters are all identical to the one used in the `hcprt` dataset. The Siemens exam card can be found [here](#), and is briefly recapitulated below. Functional MRI data was acquired using an accelerated simultaneous multi-slice, gradient echo-planar imaging sequence (Xu et al., 2013) developed at the Center for Magnetic Resonance Research (CMRR) University of Minnesota, as part of the Human Connectome Project (Glasser et al., 2016). The sequence is available on the Siemens PRISMA scanner at UNF through a concept to production (C2P) agreement, and was used with the following parameters: slice acceleration factor = 4, TR = 1.49 s, TE = 37 ms, flip angle = 52 degrees (based on Ernst angle calculation), voxel size = 2 mm x 2 mm x 2 mm, 60 slices, acquisition matrix 96x96. The field-of-view was set to cover the full brain (cerebrum and cerebellum) with an AC-PC -16° tilt. In each session, a short acquisition (3 volumes) with reversed phase encoding direction was run to allow retrospective correction of B0 field inhomogeneity-induced distortion.

3.2.2 Brain anatomical sequences

The parameters of the brain anatomical MRI sequences relevant for data analysis can be found in the NeuroMod DataLad. The acquisition parameters are identical for all anatomical sessions. The Siemens pdf exam card of the anatomical sessions can be found [here](#), and is briefly recapitulated below. A standard (brain) anatomical session started with a 21 s localizer scan, and then included the following sequences:

- T1-weighted MPRAGE 3D sagittal sequence (duration 6:38 min, TR = 2.4 s, TE = 2.2 ms, flip angle = 8 deg, voxel size = 0.8 mm isotropic, R=2 acceleration)
- T2-weighted FSE (SPACE) 3D sagittal sequence (duration 5:57 min, TR = 3.2 s, TE = 563 ms, voxel size = 0.8 mm isotropic, R=2 acceleration)
- Diffusion-weighted 2D axial sequence (duration 4:04 min, TR = 2.3 s, TE = 82 ms, 57 slices, flip angle = 78 deg, voxel size = 2 mm isotropic, phase-encoding P-A, SMS=3 through-plane acceleration, b-max = 3000 s/mm²). The same sequence was run with phase-encoding A-P to correct for susceptibility distortions.
- gradient-echo magnetization-transfer 3D sequence (duration 3:34 min, TR = 28 ms, TE = 3.3 ms, flip angle = 6 deg, voxel size = 1.5 mm isotropic, R=2 in-plane GRAPPA, MT pulse Gaussian shape centered at 1.2 kHz offset).
- gradient-echo proton density 3D sequence (same parameters as above, without the MT pulse).
- gradient-echo T1-weighted 3D sequence (same parameters as above, except: TR = 18 ms, flip angle = 20 deg).
- MP2RAGE 3D sequence (duration 7:26 min, TR = 4 s, TE = 1.51 ms, TI1 = 700 ms, TI2 = 1500 ms, flip angle 1 = 7 deg, flip angle 2 = 5 deg, voxel size = 1.2 mm isotropic, R=2 acceleration)
- Susceptibility-weighted 3D sequence (duration 4:54 min, TR = 27 ms, TE = 20 ms, flip angle = 15 deg)

.. warning:: T1w, T2w and DWI (from HCP development/aging protocol for Siemens Prisma) and SWI do not have gradient non-linearity correction applied on the scanner. Offline correction can be applied using tools such as `gradunwarp`, but is not included yet in `fMRIPrep` pipeline.

3.2.3 Spinal cord anatomical sequences

The parameters of the spinal cord anatomical MRI sequences relevant for data analysis can be found in the BIDS dataset, and included metadata. The acquisition parameters are identical for all anatomical sessions, and follow a community [spinal cord standard imaging protocol](#). The Siemens pdf exam card of the anatomical sessions can be found [here](#), and is briefly recapitulated below. A standard (spinal cord) anatomical session starts with a 21 s localizer scan, and then includes the following sequences:

- T1-weighted 3D sagittal sequence (duration 4:44 min, TR = 2 s, TE = 3.72 ms, flip angle = 9 deg, voxel size = 1.0 mm isotropic, R=2 acceleration)

- T2-weighted 3D sagittal sequence (duration 4:02 min, TR = 1.5 s, TE = 120 ms, flip angle = 120 deg, voxel size = 0.8 mm isotropic, R=3 acceleration)
- Diffusion-weighted 2D axial sequence (cardiac-gated with pulseOx, approximate duration 3 min, TR = 620 ms, TE = 60 ms, voxel size = 0.9 x 0.9 x 0.5 mm, phase-encoding A-P, b-max = 800 s/mm²)
- Gradient-echo magnetization-transfer 3D axial sequence (duration 2:12 min, TR = 35 ms, TE = 3.13 ms, flip angle = 9 deg, voxel size = 0.9 x 0.9 x 0.5 mm, R=2 acceleration, with MT Gaussian pulse)
- Gradient-echo proton-density weighted 3D axial sequence (same parameters as above, without the MT pulse).
- Gradient-echo T1-weighted 3D axial sequence (same parameters as above, except: TR = 15 ms, flip angle = 15 deg).
- gradient-echo ME (duration 4:45 min, TR = 600 ms, effective TE = 14 ms (this is a multi-echo sequence), flip angle = 30 deg, voxel size = 0.9 x 0.9 x 0.5 mm, R=2 acceleration)

3.3 Stimuli

3.3.1 Visual presentation

All visual stimuli were projected using an Epson Powerlite L615U projector. The images were casted through a waveguide onto a blank screen located in the MRI room.

3.3.2 Auditory system

For functional sessions, participant wore MRI compatible S15 [Sensimetric](#) headphone inserts, providing high-quality acoustic stimulation and substantial attenuation of background noise. On the computer used for stimuli presentation, a custom impulse response of the headphones is applied with an online finite impulse response filter using the LADSPA DSP to all the presented stimuli. This impulse response was provided by the manufacturer. Sounds were amplified using an [AudioSource](#) AMP100V amplifier, situated in the control room. Participants also wear custom sound protection gear (see section on Hearing protection above).

3.3.3 Stimuli presentation

For the HCP-trt dataset, Eprime scripts provided by the Human Connectome project were adapted for our presentation system, and run using Eprime 2.0. For all other tasks, a custom overlay on top of the [psychopy](#) library was used to present the different tasks and synchronize task with the scanner trigger pulses. This software also allowed to trigger the start of the eyetracking system, and onset the stimuli presentation. Trigger pulses were also recorded in the [AcqKnowledge](#) software. All task stimuli scripts are available through [github](#).

3.4 Physiological measures

3.4.1 Biopac

During all sequences, electrophysiological signals were recorded using a Biopac M160 MRI compatible systems and amplifiers. Measurements were acquired at 1000 Hz. Recordings were synchronized to the MRI scans via trigger pulses. All measurements were recorded and monitored using Biopac's AcqKnowledge software.

3.4.2 Plethysmograph

Participant cardiac pulse was measured using an MRI compatible plethysmograph. A Biopac TSD200-MRI photo-plethysmogram transducer was placed on the foot or toe of the participants to obtain beat-by-beat estimates of heart rate.

3.4.3 Skin conductance

Skin conductance, was measured using two electrodes, one applied to the sole of the foot and the other to the ankle, to record the participant electrodermal response.

3.4.4 Electrocardiogram

An electrocardiogram (ECG) was used to measure the electrical activity generated by the heart. The ECG was recorded using three MRI compatible electrodes that were placed adjacent to one another, on the lower left rib cage, just under the heart.

3.4.5 Respiration

Participant's respiration was measured using a custom MRI compatible respiration belt. The respiration system consisted of: a pressure cuff taken from a blood pressure monitor (PhysioLogic blood), a pressure sensor (MPXV5004GC7U, NXP USA Inc), and flexible tubing. The cuff was attached to the participant upper abdomen using Velcro strap, and then connected to the pressure sensor, located outside the scanner room, using tubing passed through a waveguide. The pressure signal was recorded using an analog input on the Biopac system, and monitored using AcqKnowledge software.

3.5 Mock scanner

Some of our datasets required a comparison between genuine in-scanner conditions and “mock” conditions, where the subject was installed in a fake scanner that reproduced the comfort and aspect of an MRI scanner. This mock setup was also located at UNF, and was equipped with a monitor screen for stimulus presentation as well as audio headphones and response devices (keyboard and video game controller).

3.6 Auditory health monitoring

In order to make sure no harm was caused to the participants' hearing, an auditory health monitoring protocol using a variety of commonly used clinical audiology tests. Baselines were acquired for each of the tests when the participants joined CNeuroMod (November 2018 - July 2019) and also at the beginning of this monitoring protocol (January - February 2021).

3.6.1 Auditory tests

The tests used during this monitoring protocol included:

- Otosopic examination
- Tympanometry test
- Stapedial reflex test
- Pure-tone audiometry test
 - Standard/Clinical frequency range (250 Hz - 8 kHz)
 - Extended/Ultra-high frequency range (9 kHz - 20 kHz)
- Matrix speech-in-noise perception test
 - First language (English or French)
 - Second language (French or English)
- Transient-evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAE)
- Distorsion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE)

- Distorsion product otoacoustic emissions' growth function
 - for F2 = 2 kHz
 - for F2 = 4 kHz
 - for F2 = 6 kHz

3.6.2 Experimental conditions

Two types of experimental conditions were developed to assess the potential short- and long-term impacts of the exposure to noise during scanning sessions. The first one comprised two separate sessions: one immediately before a scan and one immediately after that same scan. The second one comprised a single auditory test session scheduled between 48 hours and 7 days after a scan. The results acquired during the delayed sessions were then compared to the data acquired at baseline.

For more details regarding the tests, the experimental conditions or the results, see [Fortier et al. \(2023\)](#).

4.1 fMRIPrep

Results included in this manuscript come from preprocessing performed using *fMRIPrep* 20.2.x LTS series (@fmrip1; @fmrip2; RRID:SCR_016216), which is based on *Nipype* 1.6.1 (@nipype1; @nipype2; RRID:SCR_002502).

The boilerplate automatically generated by the pipeline was adapted to match our preprocessing specifics (separate anat track and online preprocessing of functional data).

4.1.1 Overview

The functional data was preprocessed using the [fMRIPrep pipeline](#). FmriPrep is an fMRI data preprocessing pipeline that requires minimal user input, while providing error and output reporting. It performs basic processing steps (coregistration, normalization, unwarping, noise component extraction, segmentation, skullstripping etc.) and provides outputs that can be easily submitted to a variety of group level analyses, including task-based or resting-state fMRI, graph theory measures, surface or volume-based statistics, etc. The fMRIPrep pipeline uses a combination of tools from well-known software packages, including FSL, ANTs, FreeSurfer and AFNI. For additional information regarding fMRIPrep installation, workflow and outputs, please visit the [documentation page](#). Note that the `slicetiming` option was disabled (i.e. fMRIPrep was invoked with the flag `--ignore slicetiming`).

4.1.2 Outputs

The outputs of fMRIPrep can be found as sub-datasets of the [cneuromod.processed](#) super-dataset. fMRIPrep functional preprocessing was run using the anatomical “fast-track” (flag `--anat-derivatives`) with sMRIPrep output described above, so as to use the same anatomical basis for all functional dataset. The output was generated in T1w, MNI152NLin2009cAsym and fsLR-den-91k spaces as defined by [templateflow](#) to respectively enable native space and volumetric or surface-based analyses.

The description of participant, session, task and event tags can be found in the *Datasets* section. Each participant folder (sub-*) contains:

- `ses-*/func` containing for each fMRI run of that session file prefixed with:
 - `*_boldref.nii.gz` : a BOLD single volume reference.
 - `*_desc-brain_mask.nii.gz` : the brain mask in fMRI space.
 - `*_desc-preproc_bold.nii.gz` : the preprocessed BOLD timeseries.
 - `*_desc-confounds_timeseries.tsv` : a tabular tsv file, containing a large set of confounds to use in analysis steps (eg. GLM).

4.1.3 Recommended preprocessing strategy

The confounding regressors are correlated, thus it is critical to only use a subset of these regressors. Also note that preprocessed time series have not been corrected for any confounds, but simply realigned in space, and it is therefore also critical to regress some of the available confounds prior to analysis. See the [fMRIprep documentation](#) for details on available confound regressors. For python users, we recommend using `nilearn` and the tool `load_confounds_strategy` to load confounds from the fMRIprep outputs, using with a standardized strategy. As the NeuroMod data consistently exhibits low levels of motion, we recommend against removing time points with excessive motion (aka scrubbing), and the `minimal` strategy available in `nilearn` is a reasonable choice. Because of the 2 mm spatial resolution of the fMRI scan, there is substantial impact of thermal noise, and some amount of spatial smoothing is advisable, the extent of it being determined by your hypotheses and analysis.

4.1.4 Anatomical data preprocessing pipeline description (<https://github.com/courtois-neuromod/anat.smriprep>)

The anatomical data was preprocessed using `sMRIPrep` pipeline. It took as input the T1w and T2w of the first 2 sessions of all participants, which were averaged after coregistration.

A total of 2 T1-weighted (T1w) images per subject were found within the input BIDS dataset. All of them were corrected for intensity non-uniformity (INU) with `N4BiasFieldCorrection` (@n4), distributed with ANTs 2.3.3 (@ants, RRID:SCR_004757). The T1w-reference was then skull-stripped with a `Nipype` implementation of the `antsBrainExtraction.sh` workflow (from ANTs), using OASIS30ANTs as target template. Brain tissue segmentation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), white-matter (WM) and gray-matter (GM) was performed on the brain-extracted T1w using `fast` (FSL 5.0.9, RRID:SCR_002823, @fsl_fast). A T1w-reference map was computed after registration of 2 T1w images (after INU-correction) using `mri_robust_template` (FreeSurfer 6.0.1, @fs_template). Brain surfaces were reconstructed using `recon-all` (FreeSurfer 6.0.1, RRID:SCR_001847, @fs_reconall), and the brain mask estimated previously was refined with a custom variation of the method to reconcile ANTs-derived and FreeSurfer-derived segmentations of the cortical gray-matter of `Mindboggle` (RRID:SCR_002438, @mindboggle). Volume-based spatial normalization to two standard spaces (MNI152NLin2009cAsym, MNI152NLin6Asym) was performed through nonlinear registration with `antsRegistration` (ANTs 2.3.3), using brain-extracted versions of both T1w reference and the T1w template. The following templates were selected for spatial normalization: *ICBM 152 Nonlinear Asymmetrical template version 2009c* (@mni152nlin2009casym, RRID:SCR_008796; TemplateFlow ID: MNI152NLin2009cAsym), *FSL's MNI ICBM 152 non-linear 6th Generation Asymmetric Average Brain Stereotaxic Registration Model* (@mni152nlin6asym, RRID:SCR_002823; TemplateFlow ID: MNI152NLin6Asym),

4.1.5 Functional data preprocessing pipeline description

Anatomical preprocessing was reused from previously existing derivative objects.

: For each of the BOLD runs found per subject (across all tasks and sessions), the following preprocessing was performed. First, a reference volume and its skull-stripped version were generated by aligning and averaging 1 single-band references (SBRefs). A B0-nonuniformity map (or *fieldmap*) was estimated based on two (or more) echo-planar imaging (EPI) references with opposing phase-encoding directions, with `3dQwarp` @afni (AFNI 20160207). Based on the estimated susceptibility distortion, a corrected EPI (echo-planar imaging) reference was calculated for a more accurate co-registration with the anatomical reference. The BOLD reference was then co-registered to the T1w reference using `bbregister` (FreeSurfer) which implements boundary-based registration [@bbr]. Co-registration was configured with six degrees of freedom. Head-motion parameters with respect to the BOLD reference (transformation matrices, and six corresponding rotation and translation parameters) are estimated before any spatiotemporal filtering using `mcflirt` [FSL 5.0.9, @mcflirt]. First, a reference volume and its skull-stripped version were generated using a custom methodology of *fMRIprep*. The BOLD time-series were resampled onto the following surfaces (FreeSurfer reconstruction nomenclature): *fsaverage*. The BOLD time-series (including slice-timing correction when applied) were resampled onto their original, native space by applying a single, composite transform to correct for head-motion and susceptibility distortions. These resampled BOLD time-series will be referred to as *preprocessed BOLD in original space*, or just *preprocessed BOLD*. The BOLD time-series were resampled into standard space, generating a *preprocessed BOLD run in MNI152NLin2009cAsym space*. First, a reference volume and its skull-stripped version were generated using a custom methodology of *fMRIprep*. *Grayordinates* files [@hcpipelines] containing 91k samples were also generated using

the highest-resolution `fsaverage` as intermediate standardized surface space. Several confounding time-series were calculated based on the *preprocessed BOLD*: framewise displacement (FD), DVARS and three region-wise global signals. FD was computed using two formulations following Power (absolute sum of relative motions, `@power_fd_dvars`) and Jenkinson (relative root mean square displacement between affines, `@mcflirt`). FD and DVARS are calculated for each functional run, both using their implementations in *Nipype* [following the definitions by `@power_fd_dvars`]. The three global signals are extracted within the CSF, the WM, and the whole-brain masks. Additionally, a set of physiological regressors were extracted to allow for component-based noise correction [*CompCor*, `@compCor`]. Principal components are estimated after high-pass filtering the *preprocessed BOLD* time-series (using a discrete cosine filter with 128s cut-off) for the two *CompCor* variants: temporal (tCompCor) and anatomical (aCompCor). tCompCor components are then calculated from the top 2% variable voxels within the brain mask. For aCompCor, three probabilistic masks (CSF, WM and combined CSF+WM) are generated in anatomical space. The implementation differs from that of Behzadi et al. in that instead of eroding the masks by 2 pixels on BOLD space, the aCompCor masks are subtracted a mask of pixels that likely contain a volume fraction of GM. This mask is obtained by dilating a GM mask extracted from the FreeSurfer's *aseg* segmentation, and it ensures components are not extracted from voxels containing a minimal fraction of GM. Finally, these masks are resampled into BOLD space and binarized by thresholding at 0.99 (as in the original implementation). Components are also calculated separately within the WM and CSF masks. For each CompCor decomposition, the k components with the largest singular values are retained, such that the retained components' time series are sufficient to explain 50 percent of variance across the nuisance mask (CSF, WM, combined, or temporal). The remaining components are dropped from consideration. The head-motion estimates calculated in the correction step were also placed within the corresponding confounds file. The confound time series derived from head motion estimates and global signals were expanded with the inclusion of temporal derivatives and quadratic terms for each [`@confounds_satterthwaite_2013`]. Frames that exceeded a threshold of 0.5 mm FD or 1.5 standardised DVARS were annotated as motion outliers. All resamplings can be performed with a *single interpolation step* by composing all the pertinent transformations (i.e. head-motion transform matrices, susceptibility distortion correction when available, and co-registrations to anatomical and output spaces). Gridded (volumetric) resamplings were performed using `antsApplyTransforms` (ANTs), configured with Lanczos interpolation to minimize the smoothing effects of other kernels [`@lanczos`]. Non-gridded (surface) resamplings were performed using `mri_vol2surf` (FreeSurfer).

Many internal operations of *fMRIPrep* use *Nilearn* 0.6.2 [`@nilearn`, RRID:SCR_001362], mostly within the functional processing workflow. For more details of the pipeline, see [the section corresponding to workflows in *fMRIPrep*'s documentation](#).

4.1.6 Copyright Waiver

The above boilerplate text was automatically generated by *fMRIPrep* with the express intention that users should copy and paste this text into their manuscripts *unchanged*. It is released under the [CC0](#) license.

RELEASES

5.1 2022-alpha

Courtois-NeuroMod 2022-alpha release includes the following sub-datasets:

- `anat` : with up to 11 sessions per participant. Updated number of sessions per subject.
- `hcprt` : 15 repetitions of the HCP tasks including some within-session. Updated event annotations, preprocessing and bug fixes.
- `movie10`: about 10h of movie watching of 4 movies with 2 movies repeated. Updated preprocessing.
- `friends s01-06`: about 60h of Friends TV series watching. This dataset is an addition to the 2022 release.
- `shinobi`: about 10h of playing shinobi. This dataset is an addition to the 2022 release. Behavioural annotations are not included, but will be part of the final 2022 release.
- `harrypotter`: reading Harry Potter in the scanner. This dataset is an addition to the 2022 release.

See the [CNeuroMod docs](#) for more details on each dataset. This release also includes continuous integration testing of the validity of each dataset.

5.2 2020

Courtois NeuroMod 2020 release includes the following sub-datasets:

- `anat` : with up to 10 sessions per participant
- `hcprt` : 15 repetitions of the HCP tasks including some within-session
- `movie10`: about 10h of movie watching of 4 movies with 2 movies repeated
- `friends s1 s2`: about 20h of Friends TV series watching

Compared to the 2020-beta release, the preprocessing has been updated, and various file organization issues have been fixed.

CONTRIBUTING

6.1 How to contribute

The CNeuroMod project is an open and welcoming community. You can get in touch through our [twitter](#), our [youtube channel](#), or our channel in the [brainhack mattermost](#).

We welcome contributions ranging from bug fixes, adding annotations or trained models to the datasets, adding pointers to useful external tools in our documentation, to suggesting designs for new tasks! We ask our community members to respect the following code of conduct. Please open an [issue](#) on the main CNeuroMod [Github data repository](#) to get the conversation started.

The CNeuroMod team is dedicated to providing an environment where people are kind and respectful to each other. This could really be the end of that code of conduct, but some forms of harassment and negative behavior are fairly hard to identify at first. Please read carefully through the rest of the document to make sure you avoid them. There is also a section to know what to do and expect if you experience behavior that deviates from this code of conduct.

6.2 Code of conduct

6.2.1 Respecting differences

CNeuroMod community members come from many cultures and backgrounds. We therefore expect community members to be very respectful of different cultural practices, attitudes, and beliefs. This includes being aware of preferred titles and pronouns, as well as using a respectful tone of voice.

While we do not assume CNeuroMod community members know the cultural practices of every ethnic and cultural group, we expect members to recognize and respect differences within our community. This means being open to learning from and educating others, as well as educating yourself.

Harassment includes, but is not limited to:

- Verbal comments that reinforce social structures of domination related to gender, gender identity and expression, sexual orientation, diet (vegetarian, lactose-free, vegan, etc), disability, marital or family status, pregnancy, pregnancy-related conditions, physical appearance, body size, race, age or religion.
- Sexual images in public spaces
- Deliberate intimidation, stalking, or following
- Harassing photography or recording
- Sustained disruption of work
- Inappropriate physical contact
- Unwelcome sexual attention
- Advocating for, or encouraging, any of the above behaviour

6.2.2 Microaggressions

Incidents can take the form of “microaggressions,” which is a damaging form of harassment. Microaggressions are the everyday slights or insults which communicate negative messages to target individuals, often based upon their marginalized group membership. The following examples can all be labeled micro-aggressions:

- commenting on a woman’s appearance rather than her work
- only directing questions at male colleagues when there are female experts in the room;
- telling someone of colour that they “speak such good English”;
- forcefully praising meat to an individual with a vegetarian diet;
- praising alcoholic drinks to an individual who do not consume them.
- Exclusion from a group can be a common nonverbal form of microaggression. Microaggressions can be couched in the form of a “compliment,” (e.g. “you’re too attractive to be a scientist”). Over time, microaggressions can take a great toll on mental and emotional health, and the target’s feeling of belonging in science and academia.

6.2.3 Enforcement

Members should seek to pro-actively eliminate behaviors that deviate from our code of conduct. If a member engages in harassing behaviour, the CNeuroMod team will take any actions necessary to keep the community a welcoming environment for all. This includes warning the offender, and potentially expulsion from the spaces administered by the community, as well as revocation to data access. We expect CNeuroMod community members to follow these rules in the CNeuroMod virtual and physical spaces. Members asked to stop any harassing behavior are expected to comply immediately. We think people should follow these rules outside of CNeuroMod too!

6.2.4 Reporting

If someone makes you or anyone else feel unsafe or unwelcome, please report it as soon as possible in person, or in writing to Pierre Bellec pierre.bellec@criugm.qc.ca or Julie Boyle julie.boyle@criugm.qc.ca. The direction will follow up with you to understand the problem, and take the necessary actions to resolve it without your direct involvement. Harassment and other code of conduct violations considerably reduce the value of the CNeuroMod research environment for everyone, and are taken very seriously. We strive to make CNeuroMod a rich and joyful community for everyone, at all time.

AUTHORS

7.1 Team overview

The Courtois NeuroMod project originated from the laboratory for brain simulation and exploration (SIMEXP), and collaborators are located at the Centre de Recherche de l'Institut de Gériatrie de Montréal (CRIUGM), CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'île-de-Montréal, as well as the Psychology Department of University of Montreal (UdeM). The team has grown to include individuals from various institutions, and in particular the Computer Science and Operational Research (DIRO) Department at UdeM and the Mila.

7.2 Funding

The Courtois NeuroMod project was made possible by a 6.3M CAD (2018-23, PI Bellec) donation from the Courtois foundation. These funds are administered by the Fondation Institut Gériatrie Montréal (FIGM), part of CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'île-de-Montréal, as well as University of Montreal. Courtois NeuroMod also includes support for two separate consortia, called CIMAQ (early identification of Alzheimer's disease), and PRISME (looking for brain correlates of the evolution of symptoms in individuals with psychosis) based at the Institut Universitaire en Santé Mentale de Montréal (IUSMM).

7.3 Team

7.3.1 Core

- Pierre Bellec, Scientific Director (CRIUGM, Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Julie A Boyle, Project Manager (CRIUGM, Québec, CA).
- Arnaud Boré, Data manager (CRIUGM, Québec, CA).
- André Cyr, Engineer (UNF & CRIUGM, Québec, CA).
- Basile Pinsard, Data Manager (CRIUGM, Québec, CA).

7.3.2 Modelling

- Guillaume Lajoie, Principal Investigator (Mathematics, UdeM & MILA, Québec, CA).
- François Paugam, PhD Student (CRIUGM & DIRO, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Yu Zhang, Post-Doctoral Fellow (CRIUGM, IVADO & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Amal Boukhdhir, PhD Student (CRIUGM & DIRO, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Tristan Glatard, Principal Investigator, Collaborator (Computer Science and Software Engineering, Concordia University, Québec, CA).

- Shima Rastegarnia, Master's Student (CRIUGM & DIRO, Udm, Québec, CA)
- Loic Tetrel, Data Scientist (CRIUGM, Quebec, CA).
- Elizabeth DuPre, PhD Student, Collaborator (McGill University, Québec, CA).

7.3.3 Vision

- Sana Ahmadi, PhD Student (CRIUGM & Concordia, Québec, CA).
- Marie St-Laurent, Research Professional (CRIUGM, Québec, CA).
- Martin Hebart, Principal Investigator, Collaborator (Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Germany).
- Katja Seeliger, Post-Doctoral Fellow, Collaborator (Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Germany).

7.3.4 Memory

- Sylvie Belleville, Principal Investigator (CRIUGM & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- François Nadeau, Bachelor Student (Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Pravish Sainath, Master's student (DIRO, UdeM & MILA, Québec, CA)

7.3.5 Emotions

- Pierre Rainville, Principal Investigator (CRIUGM & Stomatology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- François Lespinasse, Master's Student (Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).

7.3.6 Language

- Simona Brambati, Principal Investigator (CRIUGM & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Valentina Borghesani, Post-Doctoral Fellow (CRIUGM, IVADO & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA)
- Leila Wehbe, Principal Investigator, Collaborator (Carnegie Mellon University, USA).
- Mariya Toneva, PhD student, Collaborator (Carnegie Mellon University, USA).

7.3.7 Audition

- Adrian Fuente, Collaborator (CRIUGM & Audiology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Nicolas Farrugia, Collaborator (IMT Atlantique, France).
- Maëlle Freteault, PhD student (IMT Atlantique, France & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Peer Herholz, Post-Doctoral Fellow, Collaborator (McGill University, Québec, CA).
- Eddy Fortier, Msc student (Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).

7.3.8 Video games

- Maximilien Le Clei, Research Professional (CRIUGM & DIRO, UdeM & MILA, Québec, CA).
- Anirudha Kemtur, Master's Student (CRIUGM & DIRO, UdeM & MILA, Québec, CA).
- Karim Jerbi, Principal Investigator (CRIUGM & Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Yann Harel, PhD Student (Psychology, UdeM).

7.3.9 MRI sequences

- Julien Cohen-Adad, Principal Investigator (CRIUGM & Polytechnique Montréal).
- Agâh Karakuzu, PhD Student (Polytechnique Montréal).

7.3.10 Other collaborators

- Tamara Vanderwal (University of British Columbia, Vancouver, CA).
- Christopher Steele (Concordia University, Québec, CA).
- Jean-Baptiste Poline (McGill University, Québec, CA).

7.4 Alumni

- Eva Alonso Ortiz, Post-Doctoral Fellow (Polytechnique Montréal).
- Norman Kong, Bachelor Student (McGill, Québec, CA).
- Samie-Jade Allard, Bachelor Student (Psychology, UdeM, Québec, CA).
- Jonathan Armoza, Research Associate (CRIUGM, Québec, CA & NYU, US).
- James Martin Floreani, Summer Intern 2019 (École Polytechnique, France).
- Paul-Henri Mignot, Research Associate 2018-19 (CRIUGM & IMT Atlantique, France).

HOW TO ACKNOWLEDGE

We kindly ask that all publications using the cneuromod data include the following paragraph in their acknowledgement section:

The Courtois project on neural modelling was made possible by a generous donation from the Courtois foundation, administered by the Fondation Institut Gériatrie Montréal at CIUSSS du Centre-Sud-de-l'île-de-Montréal and University of Montreal. The Courtois NeuroMod team is based at “Centre de Recherche de l’Institut Universitaire de Gériatrie de Montréal”, with several other institutions involved. See the cneuromod documentation for an up-to-date list of contributors (<https://docs.cneuromod.ca>).

Data is shared by the CNeuroMod team under a [CC0 license](#). Exceptions apply for copyrighted stimuli - see readme of each dataset for more information.

In addition, we encourage you to include the name of the cneuromod data release used in the analysis (e.g. cneuromod-2020), as well as any relevant excerpt from this documentation. Although some journals flag reproductions of technical documentation as plagiarism, using a standardized wording help consistency and reproducibility in the literature. Please reproduce this documentation verbatim to the greatest extent possible, and justify to the editor that this practice does not fall under plagiarism. Note that multiple versions of the documentation exist, one for each cneuromod release, so please make sure to use excerpts from the correct version of the documentation, matching the data release used in the analysis.

8.1 Reference

[Link to the OHBM 2020 poster here](#)

[Link to the OHBM 2020 abstract here](#)

Boyle, J.A., Pinsard, B., et al. (June 2020). The Courtois project on neuronal modelling - 2020 data release. Poster 1939 was presented at the 2020 Annual Meeting of the Organization for Human Brain Mapping, held virtually.